

RECYCLING C/PPS LAMINATES INTO LONG FIBRE THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES BY LOW SHEAR MIXING

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ABSTRACT

The increasing interest in continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites has resulted in a rise of industrial waste. The recycling of this waste is the topic of this study, aiming at high mechanical properties by retaining both long fibres and the matrix material. Consolidated continuous carbon fibre reinforced PPS laminate waste was collected, shredded to flakes of 20x20 mm² on average and processed by a small scale and low-cost mixing machine at different fibre fractions. The benefit of this machine resides in a low shear mixing phase that prevents fibre breakage while heating and mixing the material well. By a piston, the extruded charge is transferred into a compression mould for forming and consolidation of plates. Specimens were cut and analysed by flexural tests. Micromechanical models were used to predict the stiffness and strength as a function of fibre orientation, fibre length and fibre content. Experimental properties of the recycled material were compared to the predicted values, to samples made of the virgin continuous fibre material and to samples made of commercially available 3 mm long pellets. Experimentally determined strength and stiffness of the recycled materials increase with increasing fibre fraction, but are slightly below the analytical predictions. At higher fibre content the properties level off, staying below those of continuous fibre laminates. Strength values show a trend similar to the one predicted by theory assuming random fibre distribution. Cross-sectional microscopic images display a disentanglement of the woven structure present in the base material. No significant difficulties were found during processing, underlining the robustness of the process studied.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Recycling of composites

Over the past decades, continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites (TPCs) have become increasingly popular. Beneficial properties, such as impact strength and fast processing, already known from discontinuous fibre reinforced polymers, result in a rising interest and number of applications [1]. Due to this increasing demand, large amounts of waste will follow in the (near) future: first in form of production waste and at a later stage as end-of-life waste. Drivers stimulating recycling come from, among others, environmental, economical and legislative reasons. For example, several European directives and regulations concern polymer waste management and recycling [2–4]. Furthermore, the cost of carbon fibre reinforced PPS (C/PPS) materials is considerably high and therefore recycling can be economically interesting.

Since the production processes of continuous fibre reinforced composites often involve activities like nesting and trimming, the generated industrial waste is considerable [5]. Whereas metal and thermoplastic materials are rather straightforward to recycle, the addition of continuous fibres to

thermoplastics makes recycling increasingly complicated. For thermosetting composites various studies were performed, i.e. Oliveux et al. [6] and Pickering [7] presented overviews of recycling routes. Thermal and chemical methods are used to separate fibres and matrix to perform fibre reclamation, unnecessary for TPCs. For both thermosets and thermoplastic composites, mechanical grinding is commonly used to reduce the waste to small particles used as filler, e.g. in injection moulding. Within injection moulding, fibre lengths are typically reduced by high shear forces to around 0.2 to 0.3 mm, resulting in reasonable fibre efficiency regarding stiffness, but low regarding strength and impact [8, 9]. Therefore the recycling of thermoplastic composites by injection moulding does not lead to structural applications. Although this route offers a solution in new applications and is likely to have a lower environmental impact compared to the current widely applied incineration method, the mechanical performance of the fibres is only marginally exploited. Since thermoplastic composites offer direct recycling possibilities by melting and forming, it opens the possibility for a higher quality recycling route in terms of fibre length and mechanical performance. This study is a practical approach to research such a high quality recycling route retaining the mechanical properties due to long fibre length, unaffected fibre sizing and impregnation, leading to a more economical and environmental-friendly solution.

1.2 Recycling solution

In order to study possible recycling routes for thermoplastic composites, Rasheed et al. [10] studied chopped woven flakes of semipreg C/PPS by direct compression moulding (DCM). In this process the material was spread in a mould, heated above melting temperature and compression moulded into the final part, before cooling down. Results showed a promising recycling route providing applications that are not feasible with continuous fibres: the geometric freedom enables the introduction of design features including ribs, thickness variations and bosses, offering function integration and geometrically optimised structures.

However, in this research thin flexible prepreg flakes were used. Applying the same method to thicker, more consolidated materials can present limitations. Stress concentrations at flake edges can lead to a large variation of strength values [10]. High fibre volume fractions are possible, but can cause problems during processing resulting in local jamming. Lowering the fibre content by adding polymer can lead to a non-homogenous dispersion of fibres in DCM, due to the absence of mixing [11]. Finally, the processing time is often long since the mould needs to transfer the heat to the material and cool it down after consolidation.

Other studies have looked at the recycling of reclaimed carbon fibres and re-grind of PPS-based long fibre thermoplastic composites and found interesting results, e.g. after five consecutive regrind trails no degradation was seen in mechanical properties [12, 13]. Although some similarities can be found, laminated material of continuous fibres were not recycled or experimental results were not compared to analytical models. However, a comparative study was performed on glass fibre reinforced PP (G/PP) [14].

1.3 Low shear mixing

In the current study, a low shear mixing approach is explored, thus overcoming the disadvantages of the DCM process described before, using a small-scale and low-cost piston blender, developed by the Centre of Lightweight Structures in the Netherlands [15]. The simple construction results in a low-cost solution in comparison to the industrial equivalent. This machine was developed to melt and mix long fibre thermoplastic (LFT) materials with minimal fibre breakage: rotating heated rods in a heated cylinder provide a double function by heating and mixing the material. Since there is no plastification screw, the shear induced on the melt is very limited and thus fibre length can be maintained. Subsequently, the charge is extruded through a piston and transferred into a compression mould for forming and consolidation.

2 THEORY

Mechanical properties of continuous fibre composites are well described by the laminate theory. However, they cannot be used for discontinuous fibre composites as their complex fibre orientations and discontinuous reinforcement is not accounted for. Adapted micro-mechanical models for discontinuous fibres were thus used in the current work and are described in the following sections.

2.1 Fibre length

With increasing fibre length, first stiffness, then strength and finally impact properties increase as shown in Figure 1. For stiffness and strength, the Tandon-Weng [16] and Kelly-Tyson [17] models were used respectively. The models assume ideal elastic conditions: e.g. possible effects of fibre-matrix debonding, interfacial slip or matrix micro-cracking are not included. A critical fibre length (l_c) can be obtained following the model proposed by Kelly and Tyson. Within this study the fibre length was kept constant at 15 mm for analytical modelling. Although the assumption of a constant fibre length suits the purpose of the current study, in practice a constant fibre length within a batch is not feasible considering the range in output of size reduction processes required for recycling. Therefore the influence of variations in fibre length will be considered in subsequent studies.

Figure 1 - Influence of fibre length on normalized mechanical properties for unidirectional Glass/PP [8]

2.2 Orientation

Micromechanical modelling was used to predict stiffness and strength based on a random two-dimensional (random2D) fibre orientation. The 'orientation averaging method' presented by Advani and Tucker [18] is applied to account for the effect of fibre orientation. An orthotropic fitted closure approximation is selected to calculate the fourth-order orientation tensors [19]: more information on the employed models can be found in [20, 21]. A modified rule of mixtures (MROM) was also used for comparison reasons. The method was modified from the classic rule of mixtures to account for random in-plane fibre orientation [22]. Typically, the MROM fails to predict properties of short fibre thermoplastics, but in a previous research by Van Hattum et al. [21] it performed well for LFT material.

3 METHODS AND MATERIALS

3.1 Materials

Three types of material were mixed and processed in this study: a shredded consolidated laminate, a powder-coated semipreg and LFT pellets. The first was a 3 mm thick consolidated laminate in a quasi-isotropic (QI) layup of 5 harness satin semipreg, with 50% fibre volume content (V_f), see Figure 2a. This material was shredded by an Untha S20 low-speed two-shaft shredder with blades of 19 mm in width and no screen, for five consecutive times. More information on shredding is available in a study by Vincent et. al. [23]. The second material was a powder-coated semipreg of 50%vf 5 harness

satin as well, but consists of a non-consolidated single layer which was cut to flakes, see Figure 2b. Both materials were diluted with Celanese Forton 0214 PPS pellets to obtain a lower fibre content ranging from 20%vf to 35%vf.. The third material was Lucovom C/PPS pellets of 24%vf, having fibres of 3 to 4 mm in length. Comparisons were made between these three materials according to the tests described in Section 3.3, as well as with virgin continuous fibre C/PPS laminates. All samples produced with the mixing device will be referred to as mixed materials, mixed plates or mixed samples and the non-mixed materials as laminate, from here on. A non-shredded laminate is tested for comparison reasons. For modelling purposes, the material data given in Table 1 were used.

3.2 Low shear mixing and compression moulding

All materials were dried for a minimum of 2 h at 120°C before processing. To melt and mix the material, the aforementioned low shear mixing machine was used. Thereafter a piston extrudes the material for further processing. The mixed melt was positioned in the centre of a 305x305 mm² cavity, see Figure 2c, and compression moulded at the settings given in Table 2, to form plates.

Property	Carbon fibres	PPS
Density (g/cm ³)	1.76	1.35
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	230	3.8
Poison ratio (-)	0.28	0.36
Tensile strength (MPa)	3530	30
Fibre diameter (µm)	7	-
Fibre length (mm)	15	-

Table 1 - Material data used in the modelling

Variable	Mixed materials
Mixing temperature (°C)	340
Heating and Mixing time (min)	15
Mould temperature(°C)	140
Dwell time (min)	3
Moulding pressure (MPa)	4,5

Table 2 - Processing conditions

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 2 – Shredded laminate (a), cut semipreg (b) and depiction of the location of charge as well as samples for flexural and microscopic analyses (c)

3.3 Testing

From the compression moulded plates, flexural test specimens (105x25 mm²) were cut with a diamond saw from the marked areas indicated in Figure 2c, and the edges sanded. The thickness was 3 mm for the laminates and 4 to 5 mm for the mixed materials, except for the 50%vf plate which was 7 mm thick. All specimens were dried for 14 h at 70°C prior to testing. Four-point bending tests were conducted according to ISO14125 at a cross-head speed of 2 mm/min. A minimum of 5 specimens for each sample was used to determine the flexural modulus and strength. The major and minor span were 99 and 33 mm respectively for the mixed plates, and 75 and 25 mm for the laminates. The 7 mm thick plate, made of the shredded laminates, results in a major span over thickness ratio of 13.6, which is below the 16.5 of the standard. Shear effects may lead to an over prediction of mechanical properties, although no dominant shear effects were observed in the failure modes. For the continuous fibre laminates, two types of samples were tested: one with the oriented fibres of the outer layer aligned with the loading direction and one perpendicular to the loading direction.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of both theoretical models and the flexural tests are presented in this section. Microscopic images were taken to visually inspect the processed materials. The results are used to study the effect of fibre fraction, material structure and processing method in order to show the potential of the presented recycling route.

4.1 Effect of fibre fraction

Results of the theoretical models and experimental flexural tests are given in Figure 3. The plots show the flexural modulus and strength as a function of the fibre volume fraction. An increase in modulus and strength for higher fibre fraction can be observed from the figures, as is generally expected. The differences between analytical and experimental data of mixed materials is small for 20 to 26%vf, but larger for 35 to 50%vf. From Thomason et al. it is known that the mechanical properties of glass fibre composites with a high fibre aspect ratio, random orientation and a fibre content above 20%vf level off due to fibre packing. A similar phenomenon will likely exist for carbon fibres, however the level at which it occurs might be different, in particular due to the smaller fibre diameter [24, 25].

Cross-sectional microscopic images were taken from the location illustrated in Figure 2c and are presented in Figure 4. When comparing the mixed shredded laminates at different fibre fractions shown in Figure 4 a and d-f, an increasing thickness is observed. At higher fibre content the mould cavity was not filled due to the increased viscosity, and since an equal volume of material was placed, the plates became thicker. Further study will focus on the influence of compression moulding settings to optimise mould filling. Another observation is an increasing fibre bundle height for increasing fibre fraction. The origin of this difference could be in the mixing and in the compression moulding step: a higher fibre fraction results in a higher viscosity and therefore reduced flow, which on its turn favours increased fibre bundle height.

With regard to the analytical models it can be seen that the 2Drandom theory predicts, in contrary to the MROM, a nonlinear behaviour for strength at increasing fibre content agreeing with the trend shown by the experimental data. Although in a previous study on G/PP using the same theory an under-prediction was observed, the current results show an over-prediction of the strength [14].

4.2 Effect of material structure

Although the structure of the input materials is very different, the plates made of cut semipreg and shredded laminate of 20%vf have very similar properties, which are also in line with the pellet material. From Figure 4 a-c, the mixed shredded laminate and mixed cut semipreg look rather similar, while mixed pellets present a higher level of dispersion. This could be related to the unidirectional structure of the pellets, in which the fibres are not restricted by an entangled woven structure. Additionally, the limited fibre length could facilitate fibre movement, as studied by Thattai parthasarthy et al. [26]. The plates fabricated with pellets tend to warp more, possibly a result of the flow-induced fibre orientation which is less constrained by fibre length and structure.

The virgin laminated material performs in line with the MROM. The orientation of the outermost layer, aligned with or perpendicular to the loading direction, is resulting in higher or lower measured properties, respectively. The virgin laminates outperform the mixed materials on stiffness and strength. Where the mechanical properties for mixed materials levels off at high fibre fractions, the laminate with a structured fibre bundle pattern does not show such effects at 50%vf. However, the design freedom when using mixed materials can enhance a part's performance due to geometric stiffening.

4.3 Effect of processing method

As mentioned in the introduction, multiple processing techniques are proposed for recycling C/PPS. These are ordered by increasing induced shear: DCM, piston blender followed by compression moulding and extrusion by a LFT compounder followed by compression moulding. As shown by Rasheed et al. [10], the DCM results in composite structures with a tensile strength of about 109 and

138 MPa for flakes with a size of 17,5x17,5 mm² and 26,5x26,5 mm² respectively at 50%vf [10]. Since these values are obtained from tensile tests, they are not directly comparable to the flexural tests performed in this study. However, the low shear mixing by the piston blender results in a flexural strength of 348MPa and a modulus of 24GPa at 35%vf, significantly higher than those found in [10]. A regrind study by Janney et al. using a LFT compounder, gives a flexural strength of 190 to 240 MPa and a modulus of 16 to 22 GPa at 34%vf [12].

It can be seen that DCM allows for a high fiber content and therefore high modulus, possibly due to compact packing of fibre bundles. But the discontinuous structure might result in reduced strength levels [27]. Mixing seems to limit the fibre content and therefore modulus, due to fibre packing problems. However, the strength is increased by the more homogeneous material structure. Nonetheless, mixing at high shear rates leads to reduced fibre lengths and therefore a strength reduction [28]. Further research is necessary to study the influence of processing in general and fibre length in particular.

Figure 3 – Flexural modulus and strength predicted by theoretical models, mixed materials and laminate.

(a) Mixed shredded laminate at 20% vf

(b) Mixed cut semipreg at 20% vf

(c) Mixed LFT pellets at 24,4 % vf

(d) Mixed shredded laminate at 26% vf

(e) Mixed shredded laminate at 35%vf

(f) Mixed shredded laminate at 50%vf

Figure 4 – Cross-sectional microscopy of the processed materials at a location shown in Figure 2. Black areas might be mistaken for voids, but are generally contaminations on the samples, see Figure 5.

Figure 5 – Enlargement of the white marked area at the arrow in Figure 4 (f)

5 CONCLUSION

The recycling of shredded C/PPS laminate was studied using a low shear mixing process to retain the fibre length and thus properties. Mechanical performance of the processed plates increases at higher fibre content, at a rate similar to analytical models, but levels off above 35%vf. For strength, this trend is in agreement with theory. This phenomenon is not observed for continuous fibre material of 50%vf. The mechanical performance is hardly influenced by the structure of the used input materials: cut semipreg, shredded laminate or UD pellets. However for the latter material a higher level of fibres dispersion and warpage was observed. No significant difficulties were found during processing, underlining the robustness of the studied low shear process, being suitable for both virgin and recycled TPCs and allowing for structural properties. Future work will focus on a better understanding of the degree of mixing, compression moulding and application of the presented recycling method.

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